

CERTIFICATE

OF APPRECIATION

TIBBIYOT AKADEMIYASI

JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Mavlanova S.A.

EFFECTS OF NATURAL FLAVONES ON MEMBRANE PROPERTIES AND

CITOTOXICITY OF HELA CELLS

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

TAQDIRLANADI

WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

